

Understanding the Role of Visual Explanations in Human-AI Collaborations in Deepfake Image Detection

MIN ZHANG[^], SORAYA KOUADRI^{*}, PATRICK WONG^{*}, MARK MCJURY^{*}, NITU BHARATI^{*}, AROSHA BANDARA^{^*}

[^] Centre for Protecting Women Online; ^{*} School of Computing and Communications, Open University, firstname.lastname@open.ac.uk

Deepfake images pose a growing societal challenge and global concerns. While artificial intelligence (AI) based technologies can support deepfake detection, the opaque decision-making of AI often limits effective human-AI collaboration. This study explores how visual explanations influence human decision-making, trust, and reliance in AI-based deepfake image detection. We conducted a mixed-subject study online with a representative sample of 381 UK residents. Findings show that visual explanations significantly increased human accuracy and trust but failed to improve appropriate reliance on AI. With more information from explanations, participants frequently over-relied on incorrect AI advice and under-relied on correct AI advice. This paper provides empirical evidence of non-experts' decision-making in detecting deepfake facial images with the presence of AI assistance and explanations. Our work contributes to a more nuanced understanding of human-AI collaboration in deepfake image detection.

CCS CONCEPTS •Human-centered computing~Human computer interaction (HCI)~Empirical studies in HCI

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Deepfake detection, Human-AI collaboration, explainable AI, decision support

1 INTRODUCTION

Deepfakes are becoming increasingly prevalent and sophisticated due to technological advantages that make it easy to synthesise content [34]. The misuse of deepfake images is associated with sociotechnical harms such as gender-based violence [18]. The rapid spread and evolution of deepfake technologies on the Internet pose urgent challenges to be addressed globally [37]. A recent survey conducted in the UK found that 90% of participants expressed concern about deepfakes [33]. Research shows that people overestimate their own ability to detect deepfakes [11]. Distinguishing real faces from fake ones is a non-trivial task for humans, making it an even more challenging use case [40].

To assist human decision-making, prior research has explored machine learning-based deepfakes detection [21,32] and the explainable AI (xAI) [22] which aims to reduce the opacity of AI systems by providing explanations [14]. However, the performance of human detection with the assistance of AI systems is mixed, with some studies showing that AI systems increased the performance of human detectors [12], and others indicating the opposite because of human over-reliance on AI systems [34]. The xAI researchers mainly focus on exploring the goals of maximising the usage of AI advice, such as increasing trust, acceptance, and understandability of AI systems, with the *assumption* that people must understand how an AI system works to “increase” their trust [39]. Recent research found that explanations may lead to blind trust in AI systems [2], and started shifting focus to the appropriate trust [24,39] and appropriate reliance [31], where humans are empowered to make correct decisions by knowing when to rely on AI systems and when to rely on themselves.

Moreover, the development and evaluation of human-centric explainable AI [19,30], particularly for non-expert end-users, has lagged behind the technological development of AI deepfake detectors. There is a lack

of a comprehensive understanding of the xAI for deepfakes detection, such as how to design effective explanations and how to evaluate them with rigorous user studies. More research efforts are still needed to provide explanations that are beneficial to users. Our work responds to this research gap by gathering empirical evidence from a mixed-subjects study, exploring the following research question: *How do visual explanations affect people's deepfake image detection?*

To this end, we created a multi-model xAI system for deepfake facial image detection [5], including both example- and feature-based visual explanations. Based on 381 valid responses from a representative sample of UK adult residents, we found that visual explanations significantly increased human accuracy and trust but failed to improve appropriate reliance on AI. Our work contributes to a nuanced understanding of how visual explanations affect human detection of deepfake facial images.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Appropriate Reliance in Human-AI Collaboration

Human-AI collaboration is when the AI system provides its advice, and humans remain the final decision maker. It has the potential to enhance human-AI complementary performance, which outperforms human or AI alone [3], but its benefits depend strongly on how humans rely on AI systems. Prior work has shown that people are influenced by AI and often accept AI's decision even when the AI was incorrect, known as overreliance [8,38]. Humans' levels of expertise can influence their decision-making [4,9]. Research [29] observed that non-experts tend to over-reliance on AI advice. This is problematic because AI is not always accurate, known as imperfect AI by the HCI community.[16,27].

Given that humans are known to be poor at detecting deception and deepfakes [6,17], AI assistance may be valuable, but only if users are able to appropriately calibrate their reliance on the system. Appropriate reliance [24,39] depends on users' ability to rely on the system when it is correct, and to reject it when the system is incorrect. However, most of the research still aims to increase trust and acceptance of AI systems [23,36], appropriate reliance and calibrated trust are under-explored.

2.2 Deepfake Image Detection and Explainable AI

Detecting manipulated images remains one of the most challenging tasks for humans [6], who often use subjective cues and heuristics to make decisions [28]. Although a range of AI-based approaches have been developed to support deepfake detection, their effectiveness in real-world contexts remains limited [37] due to contextual variability and system-level constraints, such as model accuracy [35]. Moreover, existing systems often fail to adequately communicate the uncertainty of AI detection, leading users to overlook the nuanced reliability of AI outputs. For example, a recent study tested existing warning label designs for AI-generated images on social media and found that oversimplifying the AI outputs into binary warning labels (e.g., 'fake' or 'real') encouraged users to rely on the label itself and increased false suspicion toward authentic images [13].

Explainable AI (xAI) has been proposed to bring insights into image manipulation procedures, yet prior research reports mixed effects of explanations on human decision-making. There are diverse designs and evaluations of xAI systems (see [25] for review). For example, *example-based* explanations provide exemplars, typically representatives of AI-predicted classes, and have been found useful to improve users' appropriate trust of the AI system [39]. In contrast, *feature-based* explanations provide the features that contribute to AI

predictions, and a study [10] showed that they did not improve people’s decisions and led to overreliance on incorrect AI advice. Furthermore, the evaluation of xAI systems remains a contested issue, with both the design and metrics of user evaluations having been criticised recently. For example, the commonly used proxy tasks, known as the *simulatability* test [15], asking participants to predict AI’s decision from given explanations [26], cannot represent the actual decision-making tasks [7]. Moreover, the popular evaluation metrics of xAI systems focus on subjective measures (e.g., trust, acceptance, user interpretability), highlighting efforts of increasing AI’s persuasiveness, rather than empowering users to make better decisions. In deepfake detection, relatively few studies examine how the explanation form and quality may affect user decisions.

3 METHODOLOGY

We conducted an online survey on Qualtrics. Participants were a representative sample of UK residents recruited via the Prolific [28]. The study was approved by our Institutional Review Board in accordance with standard practice. Participants were given the option to withdraw their participation at any time. The average time participants took to complete the survey was about 25-35 minutes, depending on the condition groups (*AI*-, *AI & Visualisations*). Each participant who completed the survey was rewarded £4 or £5, respectively.

Figure 1: The procedure of our mixed-subjects study. (A) Participants answered demographic questions, learned from a tutorial about the AI deepfake detection tool and three visualisations, and then their learning was tested. (B) Participants were assigned randomly to one of the groups for deepfakes detection tasks. (C) During the deepfake detection task, participants were asked to make an original decision on the shown images (Phase 1) and judged again after viewing *AI only* or *AI & Visualisations* (Phase 2). (D) Finally, participants completed a post-study survey.

3.1 Study Design

The mixed-subjects study procedure follows the design outlined in Figure 1 with four parts (A)–(D). After general questions and attitudes towards AI and deepfake detection, participants were asked to learn from the tutorial file (see supplementary materials) about AI knowledge, three visualisations (feature-based explanations) and how to interpret visualisations for a fake image and a real image (example-based explanations). The dependent variable is the condition group: participants in condition group *AI only* saw the AI prediction in phase 2; while

participants in condition group *AI & Visualisations* group saw both the AI prediction and three visualisations (as shown in Figure 2). After completing deepfake detection tasks, participants were asked to rate their experience of AI detectors and how they used three visualisations.

Participants were shown twelve different facial images in a randomised order, including 6 real images and 6 fake images. Half of the images are correctly classified by the AI detector (3 true positives, 3 true negatives), and half are incorrectly detected (3 false positives and 3 false negatives). Image selection was balanced for gender, ethnicity, and AI detection difficulty to control for potential confounds. For each image, we collected participants' initial decisions and confidence level (5-point Likert scale) before revealing the AI output (Phase 1) and again after viewing the AI output (or AI output with visualisations; Phase 2). This design enabled us to assess the changes in decisions and measure the appropriate reliance. After each deepfake detection task in Phase 2, participants rated their trust in the AI tool on a 5-point scale (1=*Very low* to 5=*Very high*). Following Schemmer et al.'s work [31], we use the following measures as the dependent variables in our data analysis:

Figure 2: The screenshot of survey tasks, phase 1 (left), phase 2 for *AI only* condition (middle) and phase 2 for *AI & visualizations* condition (right). Participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions during phase 2.

- *Relative AI Reliance (RAIR)*: Proportion of tasks in which humans correct their initial incorrect decision by following the correct AI prediction. The opposite is *over-reliance* (OR, incorrect AI reliance).
- *Relative Self-Reliance (RSR)*: Proportion of tasks in which humans stick with their initial correct decision by rejecting the incorrect AI prediction. The opposite is *under-reliance* (UR, incorrect self-reliance).
- *Overall accuracy*: Percentage of successfully identified images over total images.
- *Trust in AI detector*: Averaged self-reported trust level in the AI detector across total images.

3.2 Deepfake Detection System and Visualisations

Our multi-model deepfake detection system combines four fine-tuned XceptionNet models [5], trained on original images and processed versions using Error Level Analysis, Noise Analysis, and Principal Component Analysis. The AI detection system has achieved 92% accuracy based on the UK Home Office's Deepfake Detection Challenge 2024 [1]. For the *AI & Visualisations* condition, three visualisations were shown to participants in the tutorial and detection tasks: SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [20], Error Level Analysis (ELA), Noise Analysis, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Example of a fake and a real image with their visualisations: SHAP saliency map, reversed ELA & Nose Analysis.

3.3 Participants

A total of 491 participants responded to the survey. After removing incomplete responses, submissions under 20 minutes, and failed attention checks, 381 responses were retained for data analysis (valid return rate: 77.6%; 192 female, 187 male, 2 non-binary; age range 19-82, $M=46.5$, $SD=15.4$). Most participants were fluent in English (94.5%), held a university degree or higher (62.5%), and reported no or basic knowledge of AI (73.1%) and xAI (87.1%). The majority had limited experience in deepfake detection (89.9%), although 59.1% encountered deepfakes weekly, and the interest in deepfake detection was moderate ($M=3.8/5$, 3.8 out of 5).

4 FINDINGS - HUMAN PERFORMANCE AND TRUST AFFECTED BY VISUAL EXPLANATIONS

Overall, human-AI collaboration outperformed human alone ($t(380)=-3.82$, $p<.001$). However, this effect is entirely driven by the visual explanations condition ($t(172)=-3.72$, $p<.001$) and seeing the AI prediction alone did not significantly improve human decisions ($t(207)=-1.71$, $p=.089$). See Table 1 for the descriptive results.

Findings show that visual explanations also significantly affected participants' **reliance patterns** and self-rated **trust** level. Data analysis reveals that visual explanations made participants significantly accept correct AI decisions ($t(358) = -5.28$, $p<.001$), but also incorrect AI ($t(379)=-2.48$, $p=.014$), compared with seeing AI prediction score only. Similarly, participants significantly relied on themselves to make correct decisions when seeing AI output alone than visual explanations ($t(378) = 2.60$, $p=.010$). The analysis of under-reliance measure confirms this ($t(379)=4.88$, $p<.001$). Participants' trust level was significantly improved when seeing visual explanations than the AI prediction score only, see Table 2.

Table 1: Descriptive outcomes based on two conditions

Condition	RAIR	RSR	OR	UR	Trust in AI(SD)	AI-assisted accuracy	Human accuracy
AI only	41.2%	74.2%	14.3%	22.1%	3.35 (0.57)	60.9%	59.6%
AI&Visualizations	62%	65.8%	18.7%	14.1%	3.44 (0.63)	62.8%	59.2%

Table 2: Summary of independent t-tests comparing performance and trust assisted by AI only vs. AI & visual explanations

	AI only		AI & Visualizations		Independent t-test		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Cohen's d</i>
Relative AI Reliance	0.412	0.377	0.62	0.367	-5.281***	<.001	0.559
Relative Self-Reliance	0.742	0.309	0.658	0.321	2.599**	0.01	-0.268
Over-reliance	0.861	1.033	1.121	1.007	-2.481*	0.0135	0.255
Under-reliance	1.327	1.03	0.844	0.872	4.881***	<.001	-0.502
Overall Accuracy	7.312	1.737	7.532	1.465	-1.316	0.189	0.135
Trust in AI detector	3.317	0.57	3.441	0.629	-2.023*	0.044	0.208

*Significant for 95% confidence, **significant for 99% confidence, ***significant for 99.99% confidence, SD = Standard Deviation.

5 DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Human-AI collaboration performance and perceived trust were improved by providing visual explanations. However, findings indicate that visual explanations dramatically increased people's reliance on AI advice, regardless of correctness. This also reduced people's ability to rely on themselves to reject incorrect AI advice. Our findings expand previous work that visual explanations increased the persuasiveness of AI outputs [31] and anchored humans to the AI prediction [8] into the domain of deepfake detection. People failed to use explanations as informed evidence to calibrate their decision-making, but over-rely on AI and explanations [3,38]. Participants' trust in AI has increased with the presence of explanation. This could be particularly dangerous in high-stakes domains such as forensic image analysis [5]. Since many social media providers increasingly use automated deepfake detection [13]. This highlights the urgent need to design explainable AI to focus on supporting users in detecting uncertainty of AI (and explanations) and helping people foster appropriate reliance and trust in AI and xAI tools to make safe decisions.

In the agentic AI system, autonomous delegation and steps introduced more than just another level of uncertainty in the human-AI collaboration. The role of explanations needs to be extended to assist effective human oversight of multi-step decision-making, goal selection, and strategy reasoning, and the role of humans is also changed fundamentally. Our findings on the impacts of visual explanations on human performance might be amplified in agentic AI systems, because of increased cognitive workload and time pressure. This highlights the key challenge for human-centred explainable AI in the era of agentic AI, especially the compounding impact of imperfect explanations and the situation awareness brought across dynamic and multiple agentic processes.

Future work will examine the impact of other factors, such as demographics, expertise, deepfake detection experience, correctness of AI/xAI, and how participants utilise and interpret the visual explanations. There is no 'one-size-fits-all' explanation for all AI stakeholders [19]. Explanations may bring another layer of complexity [10]. We will take the sociotechnical systems' perspectives to design the human-centric xAI and how to avoid new types of harm caused by 'imperfect' xAI [27,35], to cope with the growing threat of deepfake media.

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